

Magnetic and transport properties of Gd and Cr co-substituted SrRuO₃

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Abstract

We explore the crystal structure, electrical resistivity and magnetic behavior of the compositional series (SrRuO₃)_{1-x}(GdCrO₃)_x (where, $0 \leq x \leq 1$) with the evolution of x , which resides between orthorhombic ferromagnetic (FM) metal SrRuO₃ ($T_C = 160$ K) and orthorhombic antiferromagnetic (AFM) insulator GdCrO₃ ($T_N = 170$ K). Crystal structure analysis reveals that complete solid solution exists only up to $x = 0.1$, and above which chemical phase separation of two/three phases occur. Electrical resistivity measurements affirm the temperature driven metal to insulator ($M-I$) transition for $x = 0.05$ and 0.1 samples. Low temperature insulating state in these samples are interpreted by electron-electron interaction of weak disordered systems. Precise analysis of temperature dependent resistivity for $x \geq 0.2$ samples (which have insulating ground state) dictate that transport phenomenon is mainly associated with the Arrhenius-type charge conduction, Mott's variable range hopping, short-range and long-range Coulomb interaction mediated hopping processes due to high degree of randomness. A strong hybridization between $4d(\text{Ru})$ and $3d(\text{Cr})$ orbital enhances the value of T_C up to $x = 0.1$. The effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) continuously increases with the incorporation of higher moment elements (Gd and Cr).

Keywords : Band and Itinerant models, Localization effects, Magneto-transport

References :

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